

Order of elemental analysis

*You can bring your samples (min 5 mg) to Sylvie (lab 07) on Mondays and Thursdays **between 9:30am and 11:00am***

Customer

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Sample

Sample name: MEM011 [Cu(6-Cl-6'-methylbpy)(POP)][PF ₆]	
Aspect / texture: Powder	
Molecular formula: 47H37ClCuF6N2OP3	Molar mass: 951.73
Used solvent: Dichloromethane	
Structure:	

Sample details

Is the sample harmful? (skin, lungs, toxic)	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Is the sample light sensitive?	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Is the sample electrostatic?	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Is the sample hygroscopic?	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Do you want your sample back?	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Additional informations:		

Elemental analysis

Sample name:

Single determination

Double determination

C <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	H <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	N <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Other elements: Cu, P, F, O, Cl		

Results

Analysis number: 2018-100			
Sample name: MEM011			
Expected values:	C 59.31 %	H 3.92 %	N 2.94 %
Results:	C 58.56 % -%	H 4.04 % -%	N 2.85 % -%
Other elements:			
Remarks:			

Date/Visa operator

07.11.2018 / Michael Pfeffer